

Studies on the Ion-Solvent Interactions. Free Energies of Transfer of Benzoic Acid and Benzoate Ion from Water to t-Butanol-Water Mixtures

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The thermodynamic dissociation constants of benzoic acid (HBz) in t-butanol-water mixtures (0-80 wt% of butanol) have been determined from pH-metric and solubility measurements. The activity coefficient values of HBz have also been calculated. But due to phase separation in the region 20-70 wt% of t-butanol the dissociation constant values are likely to be vitiated. The accurate values of the thermodynamic dissociation constants of benzoic acid have thus been determined conductometrically using the method of computation suggested by Fuoss and Kraus. The Λ° values of HClO_4 , KClO_4 and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$ have been determined in order to get the accurate values of $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}}$. The free energy changes of transfer (ΔG°) for the dissociation reaction have been split into electrostatic [$\Delta^\circ(\text{el})$] and non-electrostatic parts to have an idea regarding the basicities of the solvent mixtures. The free energies of transfer for the benzoate ion have been calculated using the ΔG° and $\Delta G^\circ(\text{HBz})$, values from these experiments and the $\Delta G^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values previously determined. The free energies of transfer of benzoate ion have been found to be increasingly positive in going from aqueous to aquo-organic mixtures. The results have been discussed in the light of ion-solvent interactions.

STUDIES on ion-solvent interactions have great importance as they are the controlling forces in dilute solutions where ion-ion interactions are considered to be absent. The changes in the ion-solvent interactions between different solvents generally cause dramatic changes in chemical reactions involving ion and have diverse applications from theoretical and practical points of view¹. One of the approaches of determining the ion-solvent interactions is to determine quantitatively the free energies of transfer of single ions from which useful conclusions regarding solvational behaviour of ions could be derived.

These considerations lead us to determine the dissociation constants of benzoic acid, a substance widely known for its antifungal activities, from conductometric measurements in t-butanol-water mixtures. t-Butanol is known for its anomalous behaviour compared to other alcohols². We also determined the dissociation constants of benzoic acid from solubility measurements, and pH-determinations of saturated solutions of benzoic acid. The study is likely to enable us to determine the effect of solvents on the dissociation constants of benzoic acid and free energies of transfer of benzoic acid and benzoate ion in t-butanol-water mixtures. The results are reported below.

Experimental

t-Butanol (L.R., S.D.S.) was treated with lime, kept overnight and distilled. The distilled alcohol was then frozen below 293 K and the supernatant

liquid was rejected. The crystallised mass was melted, and finally distilled. The middle fraction was utilised for the preparation of the solution. The weight percentages of the mixed solvents were obtained by mixing the calculated amounts of the two solvents. The dielectric constant values were calculated from the data reported by Akerlof and Short³.

Benzoic acid (G.R., E.Merck) was recrystallised from alcohol and dried. Benzoic and perchloric acids (G.R., E.Merck) were estimated volumetrically in the usual way. Sodium hydroxide, succinic acid and potassium hydrogen phthalate were of E.Merck, G.R. grade. Conductivity water was obtained by redistilling the distilled water with alkaline permanganate from all glass distilling set. Care was taken to avoid contamination of water and solvents with CO_2 . To avoid any contamination of potassium benzoate with KOH, it was prepared by adding benzoic acid in excess to that required to neutralise a known quantity of KOH solution. The solution was concentrated and filtered to remove the excess of benzoic acid; the solution was further concentrated, and the potassium benzoate formed was collected, dried and used without further purification. KClO_4 (Puriss, Fluka) was crystallised from water, dried and kept in a desiccator.

To determine the dissociation constants of benzoic acid, conductances of benzoic acid solutions at different concentrations (2×10^{-3} to $5 \times 10^{-4} M$) were measured. Similarly, for the determination of Λ° values of HClO_4 , KClO_4 and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$, the conductances of the solutions of these salts at

different concentrations (5×10^{-4} to $5 \times 10^{-2} M$) were measured in different percentages of the t-butanol-water mixtures in the way described earlier⁴. Conductance measurements were made with the aid of a Leeds and Northrup 4959 conductance bridge with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$. A 50-60 cycle signal was employed. The cell constant of the cell was determined to be 0.758 cm^{-1} . The value of the cell constant was repeatedly checked during the course of the experiments. The measurements were done at $298 \pm 0.01 \text{ K}$.

The solubility of benzoic acid in the mixed solvents was determined with the help of a Cambell solubility apparatus⁵ as described before. However, it has been observed that the method cannot be used in the range 25-65 wt% of t-butanol-water mixtures where phase separation[†] takes place. To determine the solubility of benzoic acid in this region, we took a definite amount of the mixed solvent and the benzoic acid was added in small amounts until turbidity just begins (which disappears with the addition of one or two drops of the solvent mixture). Repeated trials make the process reproducible. The amount of benzoic acid required to make the saturated solution was thus obtained from direct weighing.

The pHs of the saturated solutions of benzoic acid for each percentage of the mixed solvents were measured using a Systronic digital pH meter, having an accuracy of $\pm 0.01 \text{ pH}$ unit. Proper calibration of the glass-calomel electrode and appropriate corrections for the change in the solvent compositions were made^{6-9†}.

Results

The thermodynamic dissociation constant for the reaction

† Separation of two layer containing predominantly water and t-butanol, respectively takes place. The phase separation may form the basis of separation of t-butanol from t-butanol-water mixture. We, therefore, tried to obtain the maximum concentrations of benzoic acid present in homogeneous mixtures of water and t-butanol.

† The pH meter readings in the range 25-65 wt% t-butanol may be vitiated due to phase separation. Thus, the pK_a values from solubility measurements may be slightly in error.

is

$$K_a = \frac{C_{H^+} \times C_{Bz^-}}{C_{HBz}} \times \frac{f_{\pm}^2}{f_{HBz}} = \frac{C_{H^+}^2}{\{[C]_T - C_{H^+}\}} \times \frac{f_{\pm}^2}{f_{HBz}} \quad (2)$$

where, HBZ = benzoic acid, $[C]_T$ = total concentration of benzoic acid and C_{H^+} = concentration of H^+ ion in the saturated solutions of benzoic acid, determined pH-metrically. Since the solutions are extremely dilute ($\sim 10^{-2} M$), the activity coefficients of ions can be assumed to be unity, however, in order to get the accurate thermodynamic values, proper activity corrections were made. The activity coefficients of the ions were calculated by using the Debye-Hückel limiting equation,

$$-\log f_{\pm} = AZ_+Z_- \sqrt{\mu} \quad (3)$$

with appropriate A-values in each solvent taking into consideration the changed dielectric constants of the mixed solvents. The H^+ concentration in water was determined from the pH reading and the f_{H^+} value calculated by using equation (3). The activity coefficients of neutral benzoic acid can be assumed to be unity in the saturated solutions of benzoic acid in the respective solvents.

The solubility and the pK_a values of benzoic acid determined pH metrically have been recorded in Table 1.

The values of Λ_{HBz}^0 and K were obtained from the plot of Λ_C against $1/\Lambda$ of a number of dilute solutions of HBz utilising the equation,

$$\Lambda_C = -K\Lambda^0 + K(\Lambda^0)^2 \frac{1}{\Lambda} \quad (4)$$

The average values of Λ^0 and K could thus be obtained.

Since, the extrapolated values of Λ^0 are known to differ considerably from the real values, accurate values of Λ_{HBz}^0 in t-butanol-water mixtures were determined from the relation,

$$\Lambda_{HBz}^0 = \Lambda_{HClO_4}^0 + \Lambda_{KBr}^0 - \Lambda_{KClO_4}^0 \quad (5)$$

The Λ values were plotted against $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and extrapolated to infinite dilution to get the Λ^0 values of $HClO_4$, KBr and $KClO_4$. The plots were found to be linear in water as well as in mixed solvents. The Λ^0 values thus determined were utilised to determine the value of K.

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY AND pK VALUES OF BENZOIC ACID DETERMINED pH-METRICALLY IN t-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

t-BuOH wt%	$\epsilon \times 10^3$	A	Total benzoic acid concentration (C_T) mol dm ⁻³	Corrected pH of saturated solution	$-2 \log f_{\pm}$	pK_a
0.0	1.277 1	0.509 0	0.028 4	2.89	0.04	4.21
8.0	1.480 0	0.603 0	0.040 2	2.85	0.05	4.34
16.3	1.600 0	0.713 7	0.117 0	2.84	0.05	4.79
25.1	1.850 1	0.887 4	0.304 3	2.83	0.07	5.21
34.3	2.170 1	1.127 4	0.602 4	2.82	0.09	5.51
43.9	2.650 4	1.521 7	0.977 1	2.89	0.12	5.89
54.0	3.370 4	2.182 1	1.515 7	2.95	0.15	6.23
64.6	4.551 6	3.424 6	2.013 8	2.98	0.22	6.49
75.8	5.841 1	4.978 5	2.375 0	3.32	0.22	7.24

For the determination of the accurate values of K , the method of computation (equation 6) suggested by Fuoss and Kraus^{10,11} was used.

$$\frac{F(Z)}{\Lambda} = \frac{1}{K(\Lambda^\circ)^2} \cdot \frac{\Lambda C f_{\pm}^2}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda^\circ} \quad (6)$$

The values of the Onsager constants,

$$\sigma = \frac{82.4}{(\epsilon T)^{1/2} \eta} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta = \frac{8.20 \times 10^8}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}}$$

were calculated, utilising the η (Ref. 12) and ϵ (Ref. 3) values from the literature. The σ , θ and Λ° values previously determined were used to calculate $Z = \frac{(\theta \Lambda^\circ + \sigma) \sqrt{\Lambda C}}{(\Lambda^\circ)^{3/2}}$ and the $F(Z)$ values¹¹.

The values of $f_{\pm}$ were calculated from the limiting Debye-Hückel equation,

$$-\log f_{\pm} = A \sqrt{\alpha C} \quad (7)$$

using the appropriate values of A in different mixed solvents (where, $\alpha = \Lambda / \Lambda^\circ$).

The slopes were calculated using the method of least-squares. The values of the slopes were accepted only when the values of the regression coefficients were better than 0.995. The K values were calculated from the slopes and the known values of Λ° . The results are recorded in Table 2.

The free energies of transfer for the dissociation of benzoic acid have been calculated from equation (8).

$$\Delta \Delta G_f^\circ(1) = -2.303RT[\log K_{a(s)} - \log K_{a(w)}] \quad (8)$$

The free energies of transfer of neutral benzoic acid are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_f^\circ(\text{HBz}) &= -2.303RT \log \frac{C_s}{C_w} \times \frac{f_s(\text{HBz})}{f_w(\text{HBz})} \\ &\approx -2.303RT \log \frac{C_s}{C_w} \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

where, C_s and C_w are the molar (saturation) solubilities of benzoic acid in the solvent (S) and water (W), respectively. The appropriate corrections have been made for the dissociation of benzoic acid in aqueous and mixed solvents. Moreover, the activity coefficients of neutral HBz have been considered to be unity where the activity coefficients

refer to the standard states in the respective solvents.

However, we have also attempted to calculate the activity coefficients (γ) of benzoic acid in aqueous and mixed solvents theoretically from the available data utilising equation (10),^{13,14}

$$\log \gamma = (\delta_{\text{solvent}} - \delta_{\text{solute}})^2 \frac{V_2 \phi_1^2}{2.303 RT} \quad (10)$$

where, V_2 is the molar volume of the (supercooled) liquid solute, ϕ_1 is the volume fraction of the solvent, and δ_{solvent} and δ_{solute} are the solubility parameters of the solvent and the solute, respectively.

The molar volume of benzoic acid has been found to be 113.88 ml from the relation $M_{\text{benzoic acid}}/d_m$, where d_m is the density of the benzoic acid at the melting point (1.0713 g ml⁻¹)¹⁵. Assuming the mixed solvents to be an 'assorted' solvent of molecular weight M_s ,

$$M_s = 100 \left/ \left\{ \frac{\text{Wt\% of organic solvent}}{M_{\text{organic solvent}}} + \frac{\text{Wt\% of water}}{18.016} \right\} \right. \quad (11)$$

the molar volumes (V_1) of the mixed solvents have been determined from their density values (determined by us) and molecular weights. The solubility parameters (δ_m) of the mixed solvents have been calculated using equation (12),

$$\delta_m = X_1 \delta_1 + X_2 \delta_2 \quad (12)$$

where, X_1 , δ_1 and X_2 , δ_2 represent the mole fraction and the solubility parameters for the first and second solvent, respectively. The volume fraction ϕ_1 ¹⁶ of the solvent in the saturated solution of the benzoic acid is given by equation (13),

$$\phi_1 = \frac{X'_1 V_1}{1000} \quad (13)$$

where, X'_1 represent the mole fraction of the solvent of molar volume V_1 in the saturated solutions of benzoic acid.

The activity coefficient γ values of benzoic acid in different solvents calculated using the equation (10), are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 2—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES OF ELECTROLYTES AND DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF BENZOIC ACID AT 298 K

t-BuOH wt%	$\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2/\text{Eqv.}$				pK_a
	HClO ₄	C ₆ H ₅ COOK	KClO ₄	C ₆ H ₅ OOH	
0.0	416.60	105.70	140.40	381.90	4.20
8.0	321.60	78.37	110.00	289.97	4.36
16.3	254.25	58.00	79.80	232.95	4.74
25.1	198.90	45.50	61.20	183.20	5.25
34.3	161.60	36.60	49.65	148.55	5.62
43.9	125.40	29.70	39.95	115.15	5.94
54.0	101.65	22.25	32.57	91.33	6.41
64.6	66.50	17.90	25.60	58.80	6.88
75.8	42.85	12.95	18.90	36.90	7.30

TABLE 3—CALCULATION OF ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF BENZOIC ACID IN t-BUTANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

t-BuOH wt%	X ₂	δ _m	X ₁	V ₁	φ ₁	γ
0.0	0.000 5	23.400 0	0.999 47	18.060 0	0.018 05	1.009 0
8.0	0.000 7	23.392 8	0.999 22	19.494 5	0.019 48	1.010 7
16.3	0.002 5	23.349 3	0.997 52	21.222 8	0.021 17	1.012 6
25.1	0.007 1	23.309 6	0.992 92	23.449 3	0.023 28	1.015 1
34.3	0.015 6	23.201 0	0.984 43	26.266 5	0.025 86	1.018 3
43.9	0.028 4	23.036 7	0.971 61	29.896 7	0.029 05	1.022 5
54.0	0.049 96	22.760 5	0.950 04	34.709 6	0.032 98	1.037 0
64.6	0.075 17	22.437 6	0.924 82	40.643 3	0.037 53	1.034 1
75.8	0.106 55	22.035 9	0.893 44	50.320 8	0.044 96	1.045 7

Discussion

The theoretical values of the activity coefficients of benzoic acid in Bu^tOH – H₂O mixtures have been found to be close to unity. However, equation (10) is valid only for regular solutions which exhibit positive deviations from Raoult's law. But in case of benzoic acid, dimerisation of benzoic acid and interlinking of water molecules to benzoic acid by hydrogen-bonding are possible. These may lead to negative deviations from Raoult's law¹⁴. Thus, the calculated values of the activity coefficients of benzoic acid may differ considerably from the experimental values which are difficult to determine.

The comparison of Λ⁰ values are not possible due to lack of data. However, it has been found that Λ⁰ values decrease with increase in the percentage of organic solvents.

The change in the solubility values of benzoic acid is in the order, Bu^tOH – H₂O > Pr^tOH – H₂O > EtOH – H₂O > MeOH – H₂O mixtures^{17,18}, which is also the order of the greater hydrophobic character of the solvent mixtures. The solubility parameters of benzoic acid (δ=11.3) and Bu^tOH (δ=10.6) being very close, would naturally imply a greater solubility of benzoic acid in t-butanol compared to that in water (δ=23.0) and other alcohols (MeOH, δ=14.5 ; EtOH, δ=13.0 etc.)¹⁴.

In view of the phase separation phenomenon in the region 20-70 wt% of Bu^tOH, the pK values from solubility and pH measurements (Tables 1 and 2, respectively) appear to be less accurate, and we prefer the pK_a values determined conductometrically. The precision in the pK values is ±0.01 in water to ±0.03 in higher percentages of Bu^tOH. The pK_a values using the Fuoss-Kraus method can

be regarded to be accurate, since the conductance measurements were made using dilute solutions, and corrections for the activity coefficients of ions were taken into consideration. The method is particularly suitable for the determination of the dissociation constants of weak acids in mixed solvents, as the method is free from assumptions.

As expected, the pK value of benzoic acid increases continuously with increase in t-butanol concentration and shows a linear relationship when plotted against (i) mole-fraction and (ii) 1/ε, well upto ~60 wt% beyond which deviation occurs. It is natural to assume that the solute-solvent interactions of types other than that described by the Born equation are responsible for the deviations. Here again it has been observed that the change in the pK values is in the order, Bu^tOH – H₂O > Pr^tOH – H₂O > EtOH – H₂O > MeOH – H₂O mixtures^{17,18}. This is due to the increase in solubilities and decrease in ionisation as the hydrophobic character of the solvent mixtures increases and the dielectric constant decreases.

It is well known that the total change in the free energy ΔG_f⁰ can be divided into ΔG_f⁰(el) and ΔG_f⁰(nonel)¹⁹,

$$\Delta G_f^0(1) = \Delta G_f^0(\text{el}) + \Delta G_f^0(\text{nonel}) \quad (14)$$

ΔG_f⁰(el) can be calculated by using the Born equation²⁰,

$$\Delta G_f^0(\text{el}) = 4.184 \times 166 \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} - 0.0127 \right) \left(\frac{1}{r_{Bz-}} + \frac{1}{r_{H+}} \right) \text{kJ} \quad (15)$$

r_{H+} and r_{Bz-} have been taken to be 0.086 nm^{21,22} and 0.275 nm¹⁷, respectively. The increasingly negative ΔG_f⁰(nonel) value (Table 4) indicates increasing basicity of the solvent mixtures. The

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ΔG_f⁰(2), ΔG_f⁰(el), ΔG_f⁰(nonel), ΔG_f⁰ OF IONS IN DIFFERENT wt% OF Bu^tOH AT 298 K

Bu ^t OH wt%	ΔG _f ⁰ (2) kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG _f ⁰ (el) kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG _f ⁰ (nonel) kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG _f ⁰ (HBz) kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG _f ⁰ (H ⁺) kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG _f ⁰ (Bz ⁻) kJ mol ⁻¹
8.0	0.91	1.70	-0.79	-0.81	-1.85	1.95
16.3	3.03	3.50	-0.42	-2.45	-2.61	3.24
25.1	5.99	6.15	-0.16	-5.32	-3.36	3.53
34.3	8.10	9.54	-1.44	-7.51	-3.53	4.12
43.9	9.92	14.63	-4.71	-8.71	-4.34	5.55
54.0	12.58	22.26	-9.68	-9.80	-3.60	6.38
64.6	15.28	34.77	-19.49	-10.50	-2.23	7.01
75.8	17.69	48.45	-30.76	-10.91	-1.03	7.81

results apparently show that the basicity first increases but subsequently decreases after passing through a maximum in the region ~25 wt% of t-butanol. But in view of the limitations of the Born equation and the uncertainty regarding the radii of H^+ ion and unsymmetrical benzoate ion, the results can only be regarded to be approximate.

Since the free energies of transfer of neutral electrolyte and ions give a quantitative measure of the solute-solvent interactions, it is thus desirable to analyse the results in terms of free energy of transfer of benzoate ion. From the equation (1), we have

$$\Delta G_i^0(1) = \Delta G_i^0(H^+) + \Delta G_i^0(Bz^-) - \Delta G_i^0(HBz)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta G_i^0(Bz^-) = \Delta G_i^0(1) - \Delta G_i^0(H^+) + \Delta G_i^0(HBz) \quad (16)$$

The $\Delta G_i^0(H^+)$ values have been taken from the earlier works in our laboratory²³ and the $\Delta G_i^0(HBz)$ values have been calculated from the solubility values. The values of $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ are given in Table 4. The accuracy of the $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ depends mainly on the accuracy of $\Delta G_i^0(H^+)$ values which are generally determined using different extra-thermodynamic assumptions with their inherent limitations. It is, thus, difficult to predict the errors involved in the $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ values. The experimental values show that $\Delta G_i^0(H^+)$ and $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ values are negative and positive respectively, a fact which is generally observed in practice^{17,18,28-25}.

The $\Delta G_i^0(H^+)$ is favourable and shows a negative maximum at about 44 wt% of t-butanol. But $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ is unfavourable and increases continuously leading to an increase in solubility and the pK values. It is known that the change in free energy of benzoic acid is a measure of the tendency of two or more molecules to aggregate in solutions²⁶. The dimerisation of benzoic acid in non-polar solvents is well-known. It is reasonable to assume that benzoic acid may form cyclic dimers like²⁵

The report of dimerisation of benzoic acid in water is not available. But it is plausible that the dimerisation may be small in water and increases with the increase in t-butanol. The total driving force for dimerisation consists of two parts—the hydrogen bond formation, and hydrophobic interaction between aryl and t-butyl groups.

It is well known that the structure of water is modified by the addition of t-butanol, and this is reflected in $-\Delta G_i^0(H^+)$ ^{23,24}, ultrasonic absorption²⁴ and excess properties of mixing². But nothing specific can be said regarding the structure of the solvent mixtures from this study. It is desirable to analyse the results in the way suggested by Treiner^{27,28},

$$\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-) = \Delta G_i^0(\text{cav})_1 + \Delta G_i^0(\text{specific})_1 + \Delta G_i^0(\text{structural})_1 + \Delta G_i^0(\text{el})_1 \quad (17)$$

$\Delta G_i^0(\text{cav})_1$, representing the free energy change due to cavity formation, is usually calculated by using the scaled particle theory as deduced by Pierotti²⁹ and used by others^{30,31}. However, in view of the limitations in the calculation of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{el})$, we do not consider that the method would give more informations regarding the (specific+structural) effects. (The actual value of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{el})$ should include terms like, $\Delta G_i^0(\text{el})$ (Born) + ΔG_i^0 (ion-dipole) + ΔG_i^0 (ion-induced-dipole) + ΔG_i^0 (ion-quadrupole). Thus, the actual value of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{el})$ should be more complicated than is usually assumed). In the case of $\Delta G_i^0(HBz)$, we have

$$\Delta G_i^0(HBz) = \Delta G_i^0(\text{cav})_2 + \Delta G_i^0(\text{structural})_2 + \Delta G_i^0(\text{specific})_2$$

Though we can assume $\Delta G_i^0(\text{cav})_1$ and $\Delta G_i^0(\text{cav})_2$ to be equal, the structural and specific terms would be different for $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ and $\Delta G_i^0(HBz)$. $\Delta G_i^0(\text{el})$ would predominate in case of $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ but the dipole-dipole and dispersion interactions would be the main factors for $\Delta G_i^0(HBz)$. It is known that the calculation of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{cav})$ involves an element of uncertainty and the calculation of $\Delta G_i^0(Bz^-)$ is based on extra-thermodynamic assumptions with their inherent limitations. Thus, instead of attempting to find out the specific and structural effects, it is advisable to calculate the $\Delta G_i^0(\text{ion})$ using different extra-thermodynamic assumptions to have consistent set of values. It is also desirable to attempt a correlation of the experimental values of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{ion})$ with the different models of ion-solvent interactions.

Obviously, more data of the 'medium effect' of ions are required to obtain a clear picture regarding the ion-solvent interactions.

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